

EOSC WITHIN NATIONAL STRATEGIES FOR DIGITAL SKILLS

Landscape Report

Date of Publication: 30/10/2020

Author: LDK SA

Executive Summary

The objective of this Landscape Report is to provide an overview of the current situation in relation to national Digital Skills Initiatives in Europe. The analysis performed targeted an extended area of these initiatives, far beyond EOSC or the research sector related mapping and lied on the findings for 9 selected Member States/ Associated countries in order to provide insights on the initiatives undertaken in the field and to serve as a baseline for performing a gap analysis on the SRIA priorities.

The landscape mapping is structured upon 5 thematic areas (sections):

- a) Digital skills policy context
- b) Digital skills governance model
- c) Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level
- d) Digital Skills certification /accreditation / competence frameworks
- e) Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science

Under each section, the findings per country are presented. In addition to this, a short benchmarking analysis (comparative analysis) is also performed in order to complete the mapping of the countries. The report also includes brief country reports and factsheets for each of the selected nine countries, outlining the findings in each area per country.

The analysis indicated that there seems to be a fragmentation regarding the establishment of a governance system for the upgrade of digital skills, where focus is given in different target groups per country, mainly addressing public services users, schools, students and teachers, labour force, and business digital transformation. Hence, the identification of the most suitable approach for digital skills upgrade to target is difficult. Digital skills ecosystems are complex and, in many cases, the priorities of different actors of the ecosystem lay in silos in relation to open science and open data. No single pattern related to the stakeholder's synthesis participating in the ecosystem of digital skills upgrade is identified. Many training programmes are identified, for several target groups, both in the public and private sector, while universities offer a variety of post-graduate studies in data/bid data and statistics. DigComp is endorsed, in almost all countries assessed, as the Competence Framework related to certification of digital skills. Libraries and repositories play a crucial role not only for implementing training programmes for scientists and researchers, but mainly for upgrading the necessary infrastructure and access for open data. Moreover, it has been identified that in several scientific areas emphasis is given to FAIR data rather than OPEN, in alignment with the directions of the FAIR Data Action Plan.

In a nutshell, the major findings of the landscape analysis, in the selected countries, can be summarised as follows:

1. Governance fragmentation & diverse priorities in digital skills upgrade,
2. Absence of an integrated framework for the establishment of the competent national policy,
3. Absence of a stand-alone national strategy for digital skills in almost all countries assessed,

4. Diversification in the participation of stakeholders per country,
5. A lot of training under progress,
6. A single certification framework acknowledged,
7. A major gap assessed in combined action for digital skills and education and digital skills and open science/open access,
8. Open Science Strategies are mostly focusing on research and infrastructure,
9. FAIR Data Action Plan alignment.

2

This Study has been funded by the EOSCsecretariat.eu which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Programme call H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-4, Grant Agreement number 831644

